

Optically Active Thiolesters from S-(+)-3-Methylcaproic Acid by Arndt-Eistert Synthesis

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Manuscript received 29 August 1979, revised 3 March 1980, accepted 9 April 1980

For the first time by Arndt-Eistert synthesis the thiolesters are prepared using mercaptans. The various alkyl mercaptans react with diazoketone prepared from S-(+)-3-methylcaproyl chloride yield a series of higher homologous optically active thiolesters of the type, $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COSR}$, where R = *n*-propyl, isopropyl, *n*-butyl, isobutyl, *n*-amyl, *n*-hexyl, *n*-heptyl and *n*-octyl. The optical rotation and infrared spectra of these thiolesters have been studied.

THE synthesis of aliphatic and aromatic thiolesters have been reported earlier¹⁻⁵ by esterification of acids with mercaptans just like alcohols. Mischler⁶ found that aromatic and aliphatic acid chlorides give satisfactory results with mercaptans and aqueous alkali. Vasi and co-workers⁷⁻¹⁰ have prepared various optically active aliphatic thiolester from optically active S-(-)-2-methyl butan-1-ol.

It is likely that Arndt-Eistert synthesis can be carried out with bivalent sulphur containing compound, similar to that of the oxygen containing alcohol analogs. In view of this the present work is carried out to synthesise optically active thiolesters for the first time by Arndt-Eistert synthesis, where alkyl mercaptans are used instead of alcohols. S-(+)-2-methyl butan-1-ol (I), $\alpha_D^{25} - 4.62$, on bromination with red phosphorous and bromine resulted in S-(+)-2-methyl-1-bromobutane (II), $\alpha_D^{25} + 1.69$. It was condensed with sodium salt of diethylmalonate to form optically active diethyl S-(+)-2-methyl-1-butyl malonate (III), $\alpha_D^{25} + 4.96$, which on hydrolysis with alkali and then on decarboxylation by heating with sulphuric acid gave S-(+)-3-methylcaproic acid (IV), $\alpha_D^{25} + 4.75$. On treatment with thionyl chloride acid gave S-(+)-3-methylcaproyl chloride (V), $\alpha_D^{25} + 4.98$. The diazomethane prepared from nitroso-methyl urea reacted with S-(+)-3-methylcaproyl chloride gave diazoketone (VI) and then ketone (VII). Various alkyl mercaptans reacted with ketene in presence of silver oxide gave optically active thiolesters (VIII).

Experimental

S-(+)-2-Methyl-1-bromobutane :

It was prepared by bromination of S-(-)-2-methyl butane-1-ol $\alpha_D^{25} - 4.62$, (320 g.), with red phosphorous (20.7 g.) and bromine (266 g., 86.1 ml). The

resulting S-(+)-2-methyl-1-bromobutane distilled at 116-118°; yield 57.3%.

$$\alpha_D^{25} + 1.69; d_4^{25} 1.253; n_D^{25} 1.436$$

ether. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand at 20-25° for 3 to 4 hrs. The ether was removed under reduced pressure, and to the residual diazoketone, alkyl mercaptan (0.2 M) and silver oxide (2.0 g.) were added. The contents were refluxed for 2 hours on water bath. The reaction mixture was

TABLE 1—OPTICALLY ACTIVE THIOLESTERS OF THE TYPE

No.	Name	CH ₃ CH ₂ · $\overset{\bullet}{\text{C}}(\text{CH}_3)$ ·CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ COSR		B.P. °C	Specific Rotation α_D^{30}	d ₄ ³⁰	n ³⁰	C=O stretching vibrations	% Sulphur Found	Calc.
		R	Yield %							
								R'-C-S-R O		
1.	S-(+)- <i>n</i> -Propyl-4-methyl thiolanthate	<i>n</i> -Propyl	48.0	185-187	+1.98	0.8789	1.427	1730 cm ⁻¹ (5.78 μ)	15.86	15.84
2.	S-(+)-Isopropyl-4-methyl thiolanthate	Iso-propyl	45.0	205-207	+4.28	0.8752	1.425	1739 cm ⁻¹ (5.75 μ)	15.88	15.84
3.	S-(+)- <i>n</i> -Butyl-4-methyl thiolanthate	<i>n</i> -Butyl	49.0	217-219	+4.34	0.8792	1.427	1730 cm ⁻¹ (5.78 μ)	14.76	14.81
4.	S-(+)-Isobutyl-4-methyl thiolanthate	Iso-butyl	42.0	183-185	+2.45	0.8769	1.426	1736 cm ⁻¹ (5.76 μ)	14.79	14.81
5.	S-(+)- <i>n</i> -Amyl-4-methyl thiolanthate	<i>n</i> -Amyl	50.0	217-219	+4.53	0.8814	1.429	1739 cm ⁻¹ (5.75 μ)	13.93	13.91
6.	S-(+)- <i>n</i> -Hexyl-4-methyl thiolanthate	<i>n</i> -Hexyl	40.0	202-204	+4.88	0.8800	1.428	1736 cm ⁻¹ (5.76 μ)	13.08	13.11
7.	S-(+)- <i>n</i> -Heptyl-4-methyl thiolanthate	<i>n</i> -Heptyl	48.0	196-198	+3.58	0.8991	1.425	1736 cm ⁻¹ (5.76 μ)	12.39	12.40
8.	S-(+)- <i>n</i> -Octyl-4-methyl thiolanthate	<i>n</i> -Octyl	49.0	218-220	+2.08	0.8920	1.427	1739 cm ⁻¹ (5.75 μ)	11.80	11.76

S-(+)-3-Methylcaproic acid :

S-(+)-2-Methyl-1-bromobutane, $\alpha_D^{25} + 1.69$, (116 g.), was condensed with sodium salt of diethyl malonate; prepared from sodium (19.8 g.), absolute ethanol (350 ml) and diethyl malonate (126 g., 117 ml). Diethyl S-(+)-2-methyl-1-butyl malonate, $\alpha_D^{25} + 4.96$, was hydrolysed with a hot solution of potassium hydroxide (47.5 g.) in water (47.5 ml), and then decarboxylated by heating with sulphuric acid (44 ml) in water (110 ml) for 4 hrs gave S-(+)-3-methylcaproic acid. It was purified by distillation at 210°; yield 70%.

$$\alpha_D^{25} + 4.75; d_4^{25} 0.9679; n_D^{25} 1.433.$$

(Found by titration with 0.1 N sodium hydroxide, MW 131.5; C₇H₁₄O₂ requires MW 130.0).

S-(+)-3-Methylcaproyl chloride :

S-(+)-3-Methylcaproic acid (130 g., 1.0 M) was added dropwise during 1 hr to redistilled thionyl chloride (180 g., 1.5 M) at 10°. It was then refluxed for 1 hr and excess of thionyl chloride was distilled off. The residual S-(+)-3-methylcaproyl chloride was purified by distillation at 168-170°; yield 57%.

$$\alpha_D^{25} + 4.98; d_4^{25} 0.9675; n_D^{25} 1.432.$$

General method for the preparation of optically active thiolesters :

S-(+)-3-Methylcaproyl chloride (29.7 g.) was added to a solution of diazomethane^{11,12} in 500 ml

then cooled, filtered, dried and distilled to obtain optically active thiolester.

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to Government of Gujarat for Research Fellowship to one of us (NTN) and to Gujarat University for research facilities.

References

1. L. S. PRATT and E. E. REID, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 37, 1934.
2. E. E. REID and J. H. SACHS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 2746.
3. J. W. KIMBALL and E. E. REID, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 2757.
4. E. M. FABER and E. E. REID, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 1930.
5. I. ROBERT and H. C. UREY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2391; 1939, 61, 2584.
6. W. MISCHLER, *Ber.*, 1874, 7, 1312.
7. I. G. VASI, N. T. NANAVATI and S. B. PATEL, *J. Inst. of Chem.*, 1973, 45, 51.
8. I. G. VASI and K. R. DESAI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 837.
9. I. G. VASI and N. T. NANAVATI, *J. Inst. of Chem.*, 1976, 48, 119, 198.
10. I. G. VASI and N. T. NANAVATI, 'Vidya' *J. Guj. Uni.*, 1976, 19, 243.
11. E. WERNER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 115, 1919.
12. H. STANDINGER and O. KUPOFFER, *Ber.*, 1912, 45, 501.